

DEVELOPMENT OF ONLINE GENDER SENSITIZATION PROGRAM FOR SCHOOL TEACHERS AND ITS EFFECTIVENESS

Mr. Ketan Laxman Kamble

Assistant Professor,

P.E.S's College Of Education, Farmgudi, Ponda-Goa.

Mr. Bhupendra Bhaskar Shirke

Dnyan Ganga Education Trust's,

College Of Education -Thane.

Abstract

Sensitization means to create awareness to change the prejudices and discriminative behaviour of all the human being towards a well and equally organized behaviour to all of the individuals and groups of the individuals beyond their background in society. Gender sensitization refers to theories which claim that positive modification in the behaviour of all stakeholders, students and teachers towards children so that there is no causal effect on gender equality. Teacher is an agent of social change and a main component of educational process therefore; teachers should change themselves and take proper responsibility to make all the possible change in the society regarding gender equality, in order to bring this into reality gender sensitization of teachers should be done through online or offline gender sensitization program. Online Gender Sensitization Program (OGSP) was developed using product development method. OGSP was implemented and its effectiveness was tested on 30 school teachers of Mumbai region by convenience sampling. One group pre and post test experimental design was employed for checking the effectiveness of OGSP using t-test and effect size. It was concluded that OGSP was effective in gender sensitizing school teachers.

Keywords: *Gender sensitization, Online Program, School teachers*

1. Introduction

Sex describes the biological difference between man and woman. It is universal in nature and determined by birth. Sex refers to physiological difference between men

and women. Sex is determined on the basis of external sex organs like penis in male and vagina and breast in females, internal sex organs like testes in male and ovaries in female and chromosomes i.e. for male – XY chromosomes and for female – XX chromosomes (D'Costa, 2018).

Gender means set of culturally specific characteristics defining social behavior of men and women and relationship between them. It tells us about how we expect men and women to behave and therefore gender is a learned behavior. (D'Costa, 2018; Barodia, 2015).

Gender sensitization refers to theories which claim that positive modification in the behaviour of all stakeholders, students and teachers towards children so that there is no causal effect on gender equality (Barodia, 2015).

Process of Gender Sensitization (Barodia, 2015)

The process includes the following stages:

1. **Change in Perception** - Gender sensitization in first instance to change the perception then men and women have each other. It creates a mindset in men that no longer sees in women the stereotypical image.
2. **Recognition** -. At this stage the male folk begin to recognize the virtues of women and their importance to the family and society. There is open and spontaneous appreciation for women's involvement in multifarious activities.
3. **Loud and clear message** - The message that gender sensitization conveys is loud and clear.
4. **Accommodation** - The difference between men and women narrows down as men allows women to function in a comfortable environment in the available socio-economic space.
5. **Action** - Gender sensitized person become instrument of change as far as status of women in the society is concerned. They become action oriented and alert to see that women are neither neglected nor discriminated against and they get their due status in the society.

Need of Gender Sensitization in India (Sharma, 2017)

In Indian society there is lack of women recognition and appreciation for women's involvement in multifarious activities. The men, who are reluctant to acknowledge women's contribution, can come under the influence for sensitization to recognize their contribution. The gender sensitization process develops understanding that women do

possess wisdom and therefore they must be involved in decision making process. They have concerns and therefore should be treated with dignity and equal chance in sharing of social and economic benefits.

Significance of Education in Gender Sensitization

In India gender equality issues in education have been studied for several decades. But, gender equality in education based on systematic research is necessary precondition for formulation of inclusive educational policies that would not leave out a single girl or boy. It is therefore important to gain insight into the overall situation of teachers as well as their behaviour and attitudes towards their pupils (**Narayanrao & Gingine; 2016**). With the help of education, gender sensitization in educational institutes can create awareness among the children, parents and other members of the community about their roles in future as the men and women in the society (**Gure, 2016**)

Role of teacher in Gender Sensitization

Sarkar, 2017 says that teachers play a very important role in the early upbringing of a child as their idea and beliefs can change the thought processes of young children. Gender sensitivity training will enable them to disseminate the desirable attitude based on mutual respect and trust between girls and boys. **Sharma, 2017** emphasized that for the teachers to bring about a change in the society they should be given pre-hand knowledge over the issue. Teachers need not only know about gender sensitive curricula and textbooks but also gender equality education.

2. Statement of the Problem

To study the effect of Online Gender Sensitization program on teachers of The New Sarvajanik Education Society's High School & Jr. College, Kandivali, Mumbai affiliated to MSBSHSE Board of academic year 2020-21.

3. Operational definitions of important terms used in study

1. Online Gender sensitization Program – Online gender sensitization program means awareness The New Sarvajanik Education Society's High School & Jr. College, Kandivali, Mumbai affiliated to MSBSHSE Board of academic year 2020-21 on gender related issues like concept of sex and gender, characteristics of gender, gender equity and equality, gender socialization, concept of transgender, sexuality, gender stereotyping, sexual abuse and role of teacher and educational institute in forming student's gender identity through sessions delivered by

researcher/expert with the help of PowerPoint presentation on google meet and interaction with subjects of study through google meet chat box.

2. **School Teachers** – Operational definition of school teachers in present research is school teachers of The New Sarvajanic Education Society's High School & Jr. College, Kandivali, Mumbai affiliated to MSBSHSE Board of academic year 2020-21.
3. **Development** – In present study development means preparation, validation and finalization of Online Gender Sensitization Program (OGSP) considering feedback and suggestions given by experts.
4. **Effectiveness** – For present study effectiveness of Online Gender Sensitization Program (OGSP) means significant difference in mean scores of pre-test and post-test achieved by experimental group in teacher made test.
5. **Expert** - Experts were Teacher Educators having minimum three years experience of teaching gender, school and society interdisciplinary course in B.Ed. College.

4. Objectives of study

1. To develop Online Gender Sensitization Program for School Teachers of The New Sarvajanic Education Society's High School & Jr. College, Kandivali, Mumbai.
2. To test the effectiveness of Online Gender Sensitization Program for Teachers of The New Sarvajanic Education Society's High School & Jr. College, Kandivali, Mumbai.

5. Hypothesis: (for objective 2)

1. Research Hypothesis:

There will be significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores of school teachers of The New Sarvajanic Education Society's High School & Jr. College, Kandivali, Mumbai, after implementation of Online Gender Sensitization Program.

2. Null Hypothesis:

There will be no significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores of school teachers of The New Sarvajanic Education Society's High School & Jr. College, Kandivali, Mumbai, after implementation of Online Gender Sensitization Program.

6. Delimitations

1. This research was delimited to Gender Sensitization of school teachers.

2. This research was delimited to school teachers of teachers The New Sarvajanik Education Society's High School & Jr. College, Kandivali, Mumbai.
3. This research was delimited to school teachers of MSBSSHSE Board.
4. This research was delimited to academic year 2020-21.
5. This research was delimited to Kandivali, Mumbai.

7. Limitations

1. Response of subjects i.e. school teachers to pre-test and post-test.
2. Participation and involvement of school teachers in Online Gender Sensitization Program.
3. Internet connectivity and electricity failure during online session.
4. Internet speed, electricity failure at subjects i.e. school teachers' end.

8. Need of the study

1. There is need of Online Gender Sensitization Program (OGSP) to make teachers aware about gender related issues in classroom, school and also society.
2. Teacher is an agent of social change and a main component of educational process therefore; teachers should change themselves and take proper responsibility to make all the possible change in the society regarding gender equality, in order to bring this into reality gender sensitization of teachers should be done through online or offline gender sensitization program.
3. Considering pandemic situation due to COVID-19 in academic year 2020-21 there is need of Online Gender Sensitization Program (OGSP) as majority of teachers are engaged in online teaching from their homes.

9. Assumptions of the study

There is lack of gender sensitization among school teachers.

10. Variables in the study

- **Independent Variable** - Online Gender Sensitization Program.
- **Dependent Variable** – Gender Sensitization of School Teachers.

11. Research Methodology

The present research study has adopted mixed method research involving both quantitative and qualitative methods at various stages of research.

Table 1
Objective-wise plan and procedure of the study

Obj no.	Research method	Population	Sample/ Informant Selection Method	Sample/ Informant Size	Data Collection Tool	Data analysis tool
1	Product Development method	---	Teacher Educators as Experts Purposive Sampling	3 Experts	Questionnaire, Literature Survey	Qualitative Analysis.
2	Experimental Method	School Teachers of MSBSHSE Board School of Kandivali, Mumbai	School teachers of The New Sarvajanik Education Society's High School & Jr. College, Kandivali, Mumbai affiliated to MSBSHSE Board. Convenience Sampling	30 School teachers	Teacher made test.	Mean, SD, t-test, effect size

12. Tools and Techniques of Data Collection

Objective 1: Literature survey and Review of experts

Objective 2: Teacher made pre and post-test.

13. Programme Implementation

1. Request letter was given to Principal of The New Sarvajanik Education Society's High School & Jr. College, Kandivali, and Mumbai for conducting research.
2. School Teachers participating in Online Gender Sensitization Program – OGSP were considered as sample of experimental group.
3. School Teachers were oriented about Online Gender Sensitization Program – OGSP.

4. Teacher made Pre-test was administered on experimental group i.e. School Teachers.
5. Online Gender Sensitization Program - OGSP was implemented on experimental group.
6. Teacher made Post-test was administered on experimental group i.e. School Teachers.

14. Statistical Tools used in the study.

Experimental design was used to test effectiveness of OGSP. The data was gathered by administering pre-test and post-test of experimental group and obtained quantitative data was analyzed by statistical tool like mean, standard deviation, t – test and effect size.

15. Findings

Findings of objective 1

15.1 - After considering literature survey, suggestions of experts and discussion with Teacher Educators Online Gender Sensitization Program (OGSP) was designed.

Findings of objective 2

15.2 - OGSP was implemented to test its effectiveness, results were as follows,

Results

Table 2
t – value and Effect size

Group	N	Mean	S.D.	t value calculated	t value table	Significance at 0.05 % level (Two tailed)	Cohen's D value
Single Experimental Group	30	4.73	4.79	5.4023	0.228	Significant	0.99

Interpretation

Calculated t value (5.4023) is more than table t value (0.228), therefore it can be interpreted that, there is significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores of school teachers of The New Sarvajanic Education Society's High School & Jr. College, Kandivali, Mumbai, after implementation of Online Gender Sensitization

Program (OGSP) and Cohen's d is 0.99, therefore the magnitude of difference between the pre-test score and post-test score of experimental group is large, therefore Online Gender Sensitization Program is successful.

16. Discussion on findings

Online Gender Sensitivity Program (OGSP) was designed and implemented successfully as recommended in following research papers :

Sharma, 2017 opined that workshops, seminars, debates and gender sensitization cell should be established for teachers as they are strategically positioned to act as agents of change in order to achieve gender equality especially through what they teach, how they teach and how they role model their own attitudes, beliefs and practices in the classroom and beyond. **Lumbadi and Shongwe, 2010** in their research paper recommended that capacity building centres should be established in all educational regions intended to train teachers and conduct workshops for teachers' gender sensitivity. **T., Srivastava, Martis, 2014** and **Esen, 2013** emphasized on importance of gender training and gender equality sensitivity training for school teachers. According to **Frawley, 2005** best strategies is to equip teachers with sensitivity and awareness about gender equality because they establish face to face and close relationships with students, teachers may play a major role in the development of new criteria, roles and attitudes regarding gender equality.

17. Conclusions

From the results of present study it is proved that Online Gender Sensitization Program (OGSP) can be effectively used in Gender Sensitizing School Teachers. **(Finding 2)**

18. Educational Implications

Online Gender Sensitization Program (OGSP) should be effectively implemented on School Teachers so as to gender sensitize them so that they can come out of their own gender stereotyping and gender biasness and adopt gender neutral language, learning and teaching resources and teaching methodology.

References

- Barodia, S. (2015). Gender Sensitization and Education. *International Journal of Interdisciplinary and Multidisciplinary Studies (IJIMS)*, 2(4), 107-113.
- Best, J.W and Kahn, J.V. (2001). *Research in Education. (7th ed.)* New Delhi: Printice-Hall of India Pvt.Ltd.

- Creswell, J.W. (2012). *Educational Research*.(4th ed.) New Delhi:Printtice-Hall of India Pvt.Ltd.
- Enoc, J. O., & Gagani, R. M. (2019). The Development Of A Gender-Sensitivity Teaching Test. *Nternational Journal of Advanced Research and Publications*, 3(6), 17-24.
- Esen, Y. (2013). Making Room for Gender Sensitivity in Pre-Service Teacher Education. *International Multidisciplinary Journal*, 61(10), 2nd ser., 2544-2554.
- Gure, G. S. (2016). Gender Sensitisation: Significance of Education. *International Education & Research Journal*, 2(12), 117-119.
- Kalakoti, H. (2018, June 03). Importance of Nurturing Gender Sensitivity Through Education. Retrieved from <https://digitallearning.eletsonline.com/2018/06/importance-of-nurturing-gender-sensitivity-through-education/>
- Karade, J., & Suratkal, A. (2017). Analysis of Gender Inequality in Indian Society with reference to Pune city. *Scholarly Research Journal for Humanity Science and English Language*, 4(22), 5264-5277.
- Koul, L. (1993). *Methodology of Educational Research*. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House.
- Lumadi, M. W., & Shongwe, S. S. (2010). The Need For Training Gender-Sensitive Teachers: Addressing Education Challenges For Gender Sensitive National Development. *Contemporary Issues In Education Research*, 3(3), 41-49.
- Relevance of Gender dimensions in teaching and learning processes [PPT]. (n.d.). New Delhi: DGS, NCERT.
- Sarkar, S. (2017). Gender Sensitization and Gender Parity: Role of Education as a Vital Tool. *IJESC*, 7(2), 23007-23010.
- Sharma, R. (2017). Gender Sensitization: An Appraisal of the Roles of Teachers and Educational Institutions. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, 6(6), 38-40.
- T, R. (2014). *Understanding Gender: A training module for teachers*. Bangalore, Rajajinagar: Karnataka Health Promotion Trust.
- Valhe, P. (2012). *Homeschooling*. M.Ed dissertation, University of Pune, Department of Education & Extension.